

The Crown of Kings on the Heads of Queens? Coronation Diadem of Royal Consorts in Medieval Bohemia

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Abstract: This article reexamines the long-standing assumption that the Crown of St. Wenceslas—the ceremonial crown of the Kingdom of Bohemia—was originally intended for the coronation of both ruling kings and their queen consorts. While early modern practice and modern scholarship presume a shared royal regalia, medieval evidence reveals a more nuanced reality. Focusing on the period before and after the reign of Charles IV, who commissioned the crown by 1346, the study traces the development of Bohemian coronation traditions. Drawing on coronation ordines, inventories, chronicles, and papal privileges, it argues that the crown was conceived exclusively for kings, as suggested by its earliest descriptions and the lack of any mention of queens. The eventual use of the same crown for queen consorts, emerging in the late Middle Ages, stemmed less from liturgical or symbolic intent than from pragmatic considerations—namely, the absence of a separate crown for queens. The article highlights how such practical necessities gradually reshaped ceremonial norms, ultimately giving rise to the early modern practice of shared regalia and distinct coronation rites for queens.

Keywords: queenship; consorts; coronation; coronation diadems; medieval Bohemia; Crown of St. Wenceslas; Emperor Charles IV; Prague Castle

The Kingdom of Bohemia was among the European monarchies that established a tradition of using a ritually significant crown in their coronation ceremonies, as was the case e.g. in the Holy Roman Empire, Lombardy, and Hungary. In Bohemia, this role was fulfilled by the so-called Crown of St. Wenceslas, undoubtedly one of the most remarkable artifacts of medieval Central Europe.¹ As a symbol of the Czech monarchy, the so-called Crown of Bohemia, the diadem commanded exceptional reverence and continues to be regarded with great prestige to this day. Since its creation sometime between 1341 and 1346, it was used primarily in royal coronations but also played a prominent role in other significant ceremonies, particularly royal funerals.² The crown was last employed in the coronation of Maria Anna of Savoy in 1836, five days after the coronation of her husband, Ferdinand I, Emperor of Austria. Since then, no further Bohemian coronations have occurred, and the crown has remained unused. It is generally believed that the Crown of St. Wenceslas adorned the heads of both kings and queen consorts during coronations, beginning with its first use at the coronation of King Charles of Luxembourg, later Holy Roman Emperor, and his wife Blanche of Valois in Prague in 1347.³ In this paper, I aim to examine the credibility of this assumption by confronting it with historical sources.

¹ See e.g. Schwarzenberg, *Die Sankt Wenzels-Krone*; Otavský, *Die Sankt Wenzelskrone*; Ciulisová, *Charles of Luxembourg and his Gemstones*.

² The crown was already present at the funeral of its creator, Emperor Charles IV, in 1378 in Prague, and for the last time during the funeral ceremonies of Emperor Joseph II in 1790 in Vienna. See Šmahel, “The Last Moments, Funerals, and Graves of the Bohemian Kings,” 106; *Beschreibung des Trauergerüstes welches zum schmerzvollen Andenken weiland Seiner Kaiserl. Königl. Apost. Majestät Joseph des Zweyten*.

³ E.g. Kyzourová and Vlnas, *Žezlo a koruna*, 216–219.

Coronation diadems before the reign of Charles IV

The first royal coronation in Bohemia took place in 1086. Prior to that, the dukes of Bohemia were enthroned on a stone throne located somewhere in the heart of Prague Castle.⁴ Given the ritual's pre-Christian origins as a ceremony primarily associated with male warriors, the participation of the duke's wife was likely neither intended nor expected.⁵ The consorts became involved only after the elevation of the Bohemian dukes to kings and the adoption of coronation ceremonies, which were conducted entirely within the church and under clerical direction. At the very first Bohemian coronation, King Vratislav's wife, Svatava, was crowned alongside him.⁶ Further documented coronations of royal couples in Prague occurred only in the thirteenth and first half of the fourteenth century (1228, 1261, 1297, 1311, 1347). In 1303 and 1337, the first separate coronations of queen consorts took place, as these women became second wives to kings who had already been crowned (for a complete overview of the coronations of Bohemian consorts, see the Table).

The appearance of the Bohemian coronation regalia prior to the reign of Charles IV (r. 1346–1378), specifically before the creation of the Crown of St. Wenceslas, remains a topic of speculation. References to coronations from the earlier period are so brief that the diadem itself is rarely mentioned, and when it is, it is typically described in vague terms, usually referring only to the king's crown.⁷ Therefore, it is often unclear whether the queen was crowned with the same crown as the king or with her own. However, the Viennese annals describing the coronation of Wenceslas II of Bohemia and Guta of Habsburg in 1297 suggest the latter. According to them, the king was adorned with the “royal crown”, while the queen was subsequently crowned with a “crown of immeasurable value and beauty”.⁸

Crown of St. Wenceslas – the Kings' Crown

More sources regarding the coronation regalia emerge in the 1340s, a period of fundamental significance for Bohemian coronations. In 1344, with the elevation of the Prague bishopric to an archbishopric, the authority to crown the kings of Bohemia was transferred from the Archbishop of Mainz to the Archbishop of Prague. The associated papal privilege was issued on 5 May of that year by Pope Clement VI at the official request of King John of Bohemia (1310–1346), Charles' father, demonstrating the need to affirm the removal of the Bohemian coronation ceremony from the jurisdiction of the Mainz prelate and its transfer to the newly appointed Prague metropolitan.⁹

The charter shows that the matter of coronations was a primary concern for the royal court in Prague. It is certain that the ambitious heir to the throne, Charles, began preparing for his own coronation even during his father's lifetime, viewing it as a groundbreaking event.¹⁰ Serious

⁴ Sommer, Třeštík, and Žemlička, “Bohemia and Moravia,” 216, 227, 241–242; Žemlička, “Pražský kámen a koruna králů,” 169–180; Charvát, *The Emergence of the Bohemian State*, 109; Antonín, *The Ideal Ruler*, 342.

⁵ *Cosmae Pragensis Chronica Boemorum*, lib. I, c. 42, ed. Bertold Bretholz, 77–78; cf. *Cosmae Pragensis Chronica Boemorum*, ed. János M. Bak and Pavlína Rychterová, 143–144; *Annales Vincentii Pragensis*, 412.

⁶ For recent research on the first coronation in Prague, see Reitingger, *Vratislav*, 99–104.

⁷ *Ottokars Österreichische Reimchronik*, 916; *Cronica Aule Regie*, 122.

⁸ *Continuatio Vindobonensis*, 719–720: *...corona regali gloriose in regem Boemorum sollempniter coronatus est. Simili modo et [...] uxor eius [...] in reginam Bohemie corona inestimabili precio et decore coronata est ab eisdem archiepiscopis et episcopis devotissimis, a quibus et maritus eius fuerat coronatus.*

⁹ *Regesta diplomatica nec non epistolaria Bohemiae et Moraviae* IV, no. 1404, 569–570; *Monumenta Vaticana res gestas Bohemicas illustrantia* I, no. 393, 239–240.

¹⁰ *Chronicon Francisci Pragensis*, 200: *[...] coronatus est itaque corona illa, qua patre vivente debuit coronari, in qua inpendit plura milia marcarum. Et quia obtulerat ipsam Deo et beato Wenceslao, salutem anime sue desiderans et suorum successorum, nec non*

consideration of his coronation dates back to at least 1341, when Pope Benedict XII granted permission for the young king to be crowned by the Bishop of Prague instead of the Archbishop of Mainz.¹¹ In the following years, but certainly before 6 May 1346,¹² Charles commissioned a new coronation crown intended, like the Imperial and Hungarian crowns, to serve as a stable, timeless element of the coronation liturgy rather than being replaced *ad hoc* by newer diadems.¹³ To this end, the crown was accorded a status akin to that of a relic, functioning indeed as a reliquary for a thorn from Christ's crown.¹⁴ However, it is still unclear whether Charles repurposed an older crown or if the earlier crown was lost entirely.¹⁵

The question arises as to whether this concept of a stable crown was a novelty in the Bohemian context or whether it reinforced an existing tradition. Iconographic sources and brief historical references suggest a degree of continuity in the tradition of the Bohemian royal crown, which Charles' crown, through its archaizing design and possibly also association with the cult of St. Wenceslas—the main patron saint of Bohemia—appears to respect.¹⁶ However, it does not seem that this continuity had previously been tied to any single specific diadem. This is illustrated by the chronicler Peter of Zittau (d. 1339), abbot of the royal Cistercian abbey of Zbraslav (*Anla Regia* in Latin), who speaks with reverence about the “Holy Crown” of Hungary but pays no comparable attention to the jewels used in the coronations of Bohemian kings.¹⁷ It seems that during the rule of the Přemyslid dynasty (before 1306), the royal crown was regarded more as a personal emblem of royal dignity than as a sacred artifact or enduring symbol of the kingdom.¹⁸ As Josef Žemlička suggests, any crown placed on the king's head at the coronation could be regarded as *corona regni*. Even a crown that had previously been a private one. The transcendent conception of a particular crown as both sacred and stable becomes clearly discernible in Bohemia only from the reign of King Charles of the House of Luxembourg.¹⁹

During the intensive preparations for Charles' coronation, a specifically Bohemian coronation *ordo* was codified, later known as the coronation *ordo* of Charles IV.²⁰ This *ordo* responded to the

proventus ecclesie Pragensis ampliari, ordinavit, quod reges sibi succedentes eadem corona coronarentur et quod quilibet eorum ecclesie prefate offerret marcas ducentas [...].

¹¹ *Regesta diplomatica nec non epistolaria Bohemiae et Moraviae* IV, no. 1023, 409–410; see Šusta, *České dějiny* II/3, 348.

Unlike the privilege issued in 1344, this earlier document explicitly states that the coronation of queens also fell under the jurisdiction of the Archbishop of Mainz: *Verum quia coronatio et inunctio regis et reginae Bohemiae, qui sunt pro tempore, ad archiepiscopum Maguntinum, qui pro tempore existit, de antiqua et approbata consuetudine dicitur pertinere [...].*

¹² The new crown was mentioned for the first time in the papal charter issued on that day. Most authors believe the crown was made around 1344, see Otavský, *Die Sankt Wenzelskroner*, 29; Josef Šusta even suggests the year 1341, see Šusta, *České dějiny* II/3, 348.

¹³ *Regesta diplomatica nec non epistolaria Bohemiae et Moraviae* IV, no. 1698, 682.

¹⁴ This reliquary function is evidenced by the inscription *Hic est spina de corona Domini* on the cross at its apex, first recorded in 1355. However, the relic of the thorn is neither mentioned in any medieval descriptions of the crown nor preserved within the cross itself. Some scholars have suggested that the cross was transferred from an earlier Přemyslid crown, see Otavský, *Die Sankt Wenzelskroner*, 33–34, 48.

¹⁵ Cibulka, *Korunovační klenoty*, 40; Skýbová, *České královské korunovační klenoty*, 12; Bravermanová, *České korunovační klenoty*, 42.

¹⁶ Otavský, *Die Sankt Wenzelskroner*, 29–36.

¹⁷ *Cronica Anle Regie*, lib. 1, c. 69, 136: [...] *regum Vngarie sacro dyademate cum preclara sollempnitate festive coronatus est*. Ibid., lib. 1, c. 84, 172: [...] *sacrosanctam coronam regni Vngarie [...] de Vngaria sacram coronam [...]*. Cf. Bak, “Holy Lance, Holy Crown, Holy Dexter,” 58–62.

¹⁸ During the time of the last Přemyslids, the coronation seems to have functioned less as a constitutional act and more as a ceremonial affirmation—serving primarily as an occasion for courtly festivities and the display of royal majesty, see Žurek, “The Coronations,” 11–12.

¹⁹ Žemlička, “Rituál přísahy a koruna Václava II.,” 41–42.

²⁰ Otavský, *Die Sankt Wenzelskroner*, 36–37. Václav Žurek notes that Charles' coronation order was transmitted in the preserved manuscripts (and particularly in the Old Czech translation) as part of the work and legacy of Emperor

significant shift in the role of the consecrator and equipped the new Prague metropolitan with liturgical guidelines for conducting the ceremony, now fully independent of Mainz.²¹ By the end of King John's reign (r. 1310–1346), the organisational aspects of the Bohemian coronation had thus been substantially streamlined and clarified: the Kingdom of Bohemia acquired its own consecrator, a stable coronation diadem, and a new ordinance outlining the ceremonial procedure.

Charles IV's coronation *ordo* does not address the question of which crown should be used during the coronation. As a liturgical prescription, it references the crown only in the context of its handling during the coronation mass. When mentioning the “blessing of the crown of the king or queen”,²² it might suggest that a single crown is to be blessed, used first to crown the king, and subsequently, without further blessing, the queen. This interpretation, however, is contradicted by a much clearer directive stating that during the reading of the Gospel, following the coronation, “the king and queen are to remove their crowns”.²³ This passage clearly indicates that the *ordo* assumes both the king and queen have their own separate crowns.

However, the evidentiary value of Charles' coronation *ordo* on this matter is questionable, as the *ordo* serves as a prescriptive norm rather than a record of the actual execution of the ceremony. It is a compilation of various prescriptions that were not sufficiently harmonised. The text includes excerpts from older German *ordines* (primarily the tenth-century *Pontificale Romano-Germanicum*) and the French *ordo*, which are at times so incongruous that they contradict one another. The most striking inconsistency lies in the set of insignia intended for the queen. The Bohemian *ordo* directly quotes the French *ordo*, stating that the archbishop is to present “the queen with a sceptre, which is small and differs in form from the king's sceptre, as well as a rod similar to the king's”.²⁴ However, according to the Bohemian *ordo*, the king receives a sceptre and an orb, not a rod.²⁵ The compiler overlooked the fact that, while the French king was presented with a sceptre and a rod, in the Holy Roman Empire and in Bohemia, the orb was used instead of the rod.²⁶ As a result, the queen of Bohemia was inevitably compelled to “violate” the provisions of Charles' *ordo*.²⁷

For this reason, the Bohemian coronation *ordo* is inherently impracticable and must be approached with appropriate caution. Its text cannot be uncritically accepted as evidence of what happened in St. Vitus Cathedral without closer examination. The directive concerning the

Charles IV. Unlike other researchers, he leaned toward a later dating of the text (at least in its final form), see Žůrek, “Korunovační řád Karla IV.,” 128–130, 141. In his recent study, however, he does not defend the later dating anymore, see Žůrek, “The Coronations,” 17.

²¹ The *ordo* was edited and analysed by Cibulka, *Český řád*. His edition and study were reprinted by Kuthan and Šmied, *Korunovační řád českých králů*, 220–413. The Old Czech version of the *ordo* was recently published by Jamborová, *Korunovační řád Karla IV.*

²² Cibulka, *Český řád*, 89: *Benedictio corone regis vel regine.*

²³ Cibulka, *Český řád*, 95: *Et notandum quod, dum legitur evangelium, rex et regina debent deponere coronas suas [...].*

²⁴ Cibulka, *Český řád*, 93: *Post istam oracionem datur regine ab archiepiscopo sceptrum modicum alterius modi, quam sceptrum regium, et virga consimilis virge regie absque oracionibus.*

²⁵ For more detailed observations see Cibulka, *Český řád*, 135–137.

²⁶ Both an orb and a sceptre were used during the reign of the last Přemyslids, as evidenced by the funeral insignia of King Ottokar II and King Rudolph I, see Poche, “Zwei böhmische Königskronen”, and the description of the coronation of King Wenceslas II by Ottokar of Styria (Ottokar aus der Gaal), see *Ottokars Österreichische Reimchronik*, 916.

²⁷ On the anniversaries of the deaths of Emperor Charles IV's wives, a crown, sceptre, and orb were displayed on their tombs in Prague Cathedral, see Uličný, “Chóry,” 53. During the coronation of Queen Sophia in 1400, an eyewitness mentions a *coronam*, *ceptrum*, and *pomum cum cruce*, see Pacovský, *Svatojirský klášter*, 184–186. The presence of these insignia during the coronations is also confirmed by several medieval illuminations, see Vienna, Österreichische Nationalbibliothek, Cod. 581, fol. 84r; Cod. 619, fol. 52r; Cod. 2618, fol. 70v.

removal of crowns was copied verbatim from the French *ordo* of the early fourteenth century.²⁸ If Bohemian queens in the late Middle Ages were indeed crowned with their own crown(s), rather than the St. Wenceslas Crown as the *ordo* appears to suggest, such a practice would need to be supported by other sources.

The intended purpose of the Crown of St. Wenceslas is illuminated by its earliest known reference, dated 6 May 1346. On that date, Pope Clement VI granted Charles—his former pupil at the French court, then Margrave of Moravia—a protective privilege for the new crown dedicated to the main patron saint of the kingdom. According to the privilege, the crown could only be removed from the saint’s reliquary for the coronation of a new king or another exceptional occasion requiring the royal diadem’s presence in Prague, after which it was to be returned the very same day. Anyone who dared to steal or pawn the crown, regardless of their rank or status, would *ipso facto* incur excommunication, a punishment that only the pope could absolve. The papal privilege explicitly states that the crown was intended for the coronation of the King of Bohemia (*regem Boemie*), with no mention of the royal consorts in the document.²⁹

The St. Wenceslas Crown was already identified with the diadem used to crown Charles IV during his coronation on 2 September 1347 by the contemporary chronicler Francis of Prague, a canon of Metropolitan Chapter of St. Vitus. He records that Charles was “crowned with the crown that he was to have been crowned with during his father’s lifetime and for which he spent many thousand marks” and that the king decreed this crown, which he “dedicated to God and St. Wenceslas,” should be used to crown “the kings who would follow him.”³⁰ Similarly, the chronicler Beneš Krabice of Weitmühl, also a canon of Prague Cathedral, states that “the king then donated the crown with which he had been crowned to St. Wenceslas, to be placed on his head in the Prague Church on certain days, decreeing that all kings of Bohemia, his successors, must be crowned with the same crown.”³¹ Neither chronicler makes any mention of the king’s wife being, or intended to be, crowned with this crown.

Since the crown was part of the treasury of Prague Cathedral, it appears regularly in its medieval inventories. The 1355 inventory records that the emperor donated this crown to the cathedral “for the adornment of St. Wenceslas’ head” and that “it is to be used to crown Bohemian kings”.³² The 1368 inventory notes that the crown is lent for the coronation of kings, with a requirement for the kings to donate two hundred marks to the church each time they are crowned.³³ Along with the crown and many other items, the 1355 inventory also lists a crystal vial

²⁸ Cibulka, *Český řád*, 67, 73.

²⁹ *Monumenta Vaticana res gestas Bohemicas illustrantia* I, no. 650, 386: [...] *de novo fieri fecit quoddam satis preciosum regium diadema illudque glorioso capiti dicti sancti, cuius corpus in Pragensi requiescit ecclesia, donavit et fecit apponi ea intentione, ut ab ipso capite non debeat amoveri, nisi dumtaxat quando regem Boemie, qui pro tempore fuerit, de novo coronari vel alia per eundem regem solennia, que regalis diadematis usum exigerent, in civitate vel suburbiis Pragensibus, solenniter contingeret celebrari, quo casu liceret prefato regi diadema ipsum recipere, sic tamen, quod ipsum eadem die coronationis vel celebrationis huiusmodi eidem beato capiti reponere teneatur.*

³⁰ *Chronicon Francisci Pragensis*, 200: [...] *coronatus est itaque corona illa, qua patre vivente debuit coronari, in qua inpendit plura milia marcarum. Et quia obtulerat ipsam Deo et beato Wenceslao, salutem anime sue desiderans et suorum successorum nec non proventus ecclesie Pragensis ampliare, ordinavit, quod reges sibi succedentes eadem corona coronarentur et quod quilibet eorum ecclesie prefate offerret marcas ducentas [...].*

³¹ *Chronicon Benessi de Weitmil*, 515: *Coronam autem, qua ipse rex coronatus est, donavit sancto Wenceslao, eius capiti in ecclesia Pragensi certis diebus imponendam, decernens, ut omnes reges Boemie sui successores eadem debeant corona coronari.*

³² Podlaha and Sittler, *Chrámový poklad*, XVII, no. 176: [...] *quam coronam praefatus dominus imperator donavit ecclesiae Pragensi pro ornamento capitis sancti Wenceslai, cum qua deinceps reges debent coronari.*

³³ Podlaha and Sittler, *Chrámový poklad*, XVII, note 11: *Quae conceditur regibus coronandis, qui reges debent dare CC marchas ecclesiae Pragensi, et hoc, quoties cum eadem coronantur.*

containing the holy oil “for anointing the kings.”³⁴ Interestingly, the 1354 inventory explicitly states that this oil is used for anointing both “kings of Bohemia and queens.”³⁵ This raises the question of whether queens were similarly omitted in references to the St. Wenceslas Crown, as in the case of the oil vial in the 1355 inventory, or whether this silence holds deeper significance. In my opinion, the consistent omission of queens in so many fourteenth-century sources strongly suggests that, according to Charles’ original intention, the St. Wenceslas Crown was meant to rest solely on the heads of kings, not their wives.

Yet, the striking absence of evidence regarding the use of the St. Wenceslas Crown in the coronations of queens during the fourteenth century, as well as the brief note in the *ordo* of Charles IV stating that both the king and queen should remove “their crowns” during the Gospel reading, are not sufficient proof that the queens in medieval Bohemia were, in fact, crowned with a different crown than the king.

Separate Coronations of the Queens

If the Bohemian coronation rite underwent such a significant transformation that queens began to be crowned with the same crown as kings—a standard practice in early modern Bohemia—what might have prompted this change? It may be closely linked to another notable shift that took place between the coronations of Bohemian queens in the Middle Ages and the early modern period. In the earliest times, queen consorts were crowned together with their husbands during the same mass—a practice codified in the coronation *ordo* of Charles IV—while only second wives underwent a separate ceremony. However, in later periods, the queen’s coronation was always held separately from the king’s, during an independent coronation mass. The last king to be crowned alongside his wife, in accordance with Charles’ coronation *ordo*, was paradoxically the *ordo*’s author himself.

The coronation of Charles IV and Blanche of Valois in 1347 marked the end of the long-standing tradition of joint coronations for royal spouses, even though Charles likely believed that formalizing this practice in a new coronation *ordo* would ensure its continuation for centuries. The next royal couple to undergo a coronation was George of Poděbrady and Johana of Rožmitál, nearly a century later, in 1458. In defiance of both established tradition and the Bohemian coronation *ordo*, Johana was crowned a day after her husband. From then on, all subsequent queens were crowned separately, a practice that continued until the nineteenth century. The cause of this deviation has remained unclear so far,³⁶ given that the separation of the queen’s coronation from the king’s did not align with any known European trend.³⁷

An explanation for this unprecedented change can be relatively simple: The need to separate the coronation into two distinct ceremonies arose because, at that time, no other diadem was available in Prague with which the queen could be crowned, apart from the St. Wenceslas Crown.³⁸ The presence of only one coronation jewel made a joint coronation of the royal spouses practically impossible. This would have resulted in the absurd situation where the newly crowned

³⁴ Podlaha and Šittler, *Chrámový poklad*, XVI, no. 149: *Vasculum cristalinum ad modum pyxididis, in quo portatur crisma ad unguendos reges, per prefatum dominum imperatorem donatum.*

³⁵ Podlaha and Šittler, *Chrámový poklad*, III–IV, no. 20: *Item vasculum cristalinum pro repositione crismatis sive olei sacri pro unctione regum Bohemiae et reginarum, quam idem rex pro coronacionibus ipsorum dedit et reservari mandavit.*

³⁶ Žůrek, “The Coronations,” 29.

³⁷ For example, in neighbouring Poland, the ceremony was never divided. Queens were crowned alongside their husbands until the last coronation of a Polish queen in 1734, see Rožek, *Polskie koronacje i korony*, 150.

³⁸ The presence of a single crown during the coronation festivities of 1458 is suggested by the testimony in the book of the deans of the Faculty of Arts of Prague University, see *Liber decanorum facultatis philosophicae Universitatis Pragensis* II, 59, see also its facsimile by Beránek, Černý, and Pravdová, *Liber decanorum*, fol. 140v.

king would immediately have had his crown removed to be placed on his wife's head, raising the question of how the two crowned heads could share the same crown. In contrast, in those monarchies where royal spouses were traditionally crowned together, each was given their own crown.³⁹ To avoid the undignified sharing of one crown, Queen Johana had to wait a day for her coronation in 1458. By the time another royal couple was crowned in Prague in 1527, the medieval tradition of joint coronations with separate crowns for the spouses had been entirely forgotten. In this and all later coronations until 1836, the queen consort was crowned with the St. Wenceslas Crown one or several days after the coronation of her reigning husband.⁴⁰

The coronation held in Prague in 1458 was not the first to feature only a single royal crown. As early as 1337, Abbot Peter of Zittau had criticised that the coronation of Beatrice of Bourbon for lacking the customary splendour. He expressed surprise that the queen had been crowned with “the crown of the Kingdom of Bohemia” (*corona regni Boemie*) and that King John had taken part in the ceremony without a crown or any royal regalia of his own.⁴¹ It seems that John of Luxembourg—who had been crowned alongside his first wife, Elizabeth of Bohemia, in 1311—had used his own crown for Beatrice, because no other diadem was available. Even the coronation feast, Peter observed, was notably modest.

Peter's indignation offers valuable insight into contemporary expectations. In his day, it was not the norm for a king and queen to share a single crown; he regarded this as a sign of waning royal grandeur. His account suggests that, during the late thirteenth and early fourteenth centuries, royal couples were crowned with two distinct crowns. For example, at Elizabeth Richeza's independent coronation in 1303, her husband, King Wenceslas II, wore his own crown—unlike King John at Beatrice's ceremony.⁴² According to Peter's chronicle of Zbraslav Abbey, it was customary for a queen to be crowned with her own crown, distinct from the king's. When Charles IV had Blanche of Valois crowned alongside him in 1347, he surely sought to avoid the criticised negligence of his father.

Crowns of Bohemian Queens in the Luxembourg Era

This evidence strongly supports the conclusion that the St. Wenceslas Crown was designed exclusively for the coronation of reigning kings and that, at least in the case of Blanche of Valois, she could not have been crowned with the same crown as her husband. This prompts the question: with which crown were queens crowned? Was there another diadem in Prague that could have been used to adorn queens? The scandalous presence of a single usable crown at the Prague court in 1337 was clearly a rare anomaly. By contrast, the later court of Charles IV undoubtedly possessed several diadems.

The inventories of the treasury of St. Vitus Cathedral in Prague provide compelling evidence. In 1354, they record a gold crown adorned with gemstones, donated to embellish the tomb of St.

³⁹ This is the case of England, where the St. Edward's Crown was traditionally used to crown reigning kings, with the sole exception being its use in 1533 at the separate coronation of Anne Boleyn, see Twining, *A History of the Crown Jewels*, 138. Although in Hungary, queens were crowned with their own crowns, their shoulders were touched with the Holy Crown of the kings, a practice first recorded in 1563, see Bak and Pálffy, *Crown and coronation in Hungary*, 97. This may explain why the coronations of Hungarian queens also became separate ceremonies from the sixteenth to the eighteenth century.

⁴⁰ Hrbek, *České barokní korunovace*, 98.

⁴¹ *Cronica Aule Regie*, lib. 3, c. 14, 536–537: *Eodem anno XV^o Kalendas Iunii Beatrix regina in castro Pragensi ab Iohanne eiusdem ecclesie episcopo die dominico non cum tanta solempnitate celebri, quantam nos alias priori tempore vidimus in huiusmodi coronacionibus fieri, corona regni Boemie coronatur Iohanne rege sine corona et absque regalibus induiis assistente*. Cf. *Chronicon Francisci Pragensis*, 166: [...] *non cum tanta celebri solempnitate, sicut in coronacionibus fieri consuevit*.

⁴² *Cronica Aule Regie*, lib. 1, c. 69, 139.

Wenceslas.⁴³ According to the inventory, the crown originally belonged to Queen Anna, most likely Anna of Bavaria (r. 1349–1353), the second wife of Charles IV who died in 1353, rather than his third wife, Anna of Świdnica (r. 1353–1362). This identification is supported by another entry in the same inventory, which describes a rare curtain donated “after the death of Lady Anna, Queen of the Romans and Bohemia.”⁴⁴ Additionally, the 1368 inventory notes that Charles’ daughter, Catharine, Margravine of Brandenburg, contributed a lavishly decorated crown, described as a “ceremonial crown full of gems and pearls,” which was donated for the reliquary head of St. Sigismund.⁴⁵

Donations of valuable items to the cathedral in connection with significant events were a common practice. In addition to those associated with funerals, there is also evidence of gifts made following coronations. For instance, Queen Sophia of Bavaria donated the fabrics from the canopies used during her coronation in 1400, from which the Prague Metropolitan Chapter crafted two black chasubles.⁴⁶ It was not uncommon for a king or queen to donate or “offer” their crown to a church.⁴⁷ Such a crown could have adorned the liturgical space permanently or been displayed during specific feast days. Alternatively, its material might have been repurposed for other pious purposes. In some cases, crowns were reused for later coronations. For example, during the twelfth and thirteenth centuries, the Abbey of Saint-Denis became the treasury for French regalia.⁴⁸

There are also two reliquary busts adorned with royal crowns, still preserved in Aachen, Germany, which may have been donated directly by Emperor Charles IV. One of these crowns decorates the reliquary bust for the arm of St. John the Baptist, created after 1355 for the Cistercian nunnery in Burtscheid.⁴⁹ The other is linked to the reliquary bust of Charlemagne in Aachen Cathedral, crafted before 1376. Unfortunately, scholarly opinions on the origins of the Aachen crown vary widely.⁵⁰ Some researchers suggest that it might have been a personal crown of Charles IV, used during his coronation as King of the Romans,⁵¹ or perhaps an older Bohemian crown once worn by King Wenceslas II.⁵²

Between 1985 and 1988, a remarkable discovery was made in Środa Śląska, Poland, during construction work on the site of a former Jewish quarter that had been plundered in 1362. A golden woman’s crown, likely crafted in the early fourteenth century in France or Southern Europe, was unearthed. Given the historical context, it is plausible that the crown originally belonged to the Bohemian royal court before being pawned or sold by Charles IV to local Jewish merchants.⁵³ Could this crown be directly associated with Queen Blanche of Valois (d. 1348),

⁴³ Podlaha and Šittler, *Chrámový poklad*, IV, no. 25: *Corona aurea cum gemmis pro decore sepulcri sancti Wencezslai donata, quae fuit reginae Annae.*

⁴⁴ Cf. Podlaha and Šittler, *Chrámový poklad*, 49 and VII, no. 226: *Item chortina de sex balkinis cum diversis armis circum, quae est data post mortem dominae Annae, reginae Romanorum et Boemiae reginae.*

⁴⁵ Podlaha and Šittler, *Chrámový poklad*, XXVII, no. 23: *Item accrevit corona sollempnis plena gemmis et perlis, donata pro capite sancti Sigismundi per filiam domini imperatoris, marchionissam Brandeburgensem.*

⁴⁶ Podlaha and Šittler, *Chrámový poklad*, 77 and XXXIX, no. 244, note 2: *Item duae casulae nigrae in brunatico campo, quae per capitulum factae de balkinis, post coronationem reginae datae.*

⁴⁷ E.g. Queen Gisela of Hungary donated her coronation crown to the cathedral of Veszprém, see Bak and Pálffy, *Crown*, 93.

⁴⁸ Reitinger, “Die königlichen Insignien,” 115–130.

⁴⁹ Boehm and Fajt, *Prague: The Crown of Bohemia*, 153.

⁵⁰ Kodišová, “Materiály ke zlatnictví na dvoře Karla IV.” 123–129; Gregorová, Bohatý, Stehlíková, and Duffin, “Crapaudine’ (Scheentia teeth) – the jewel of Kings,” 278.

⁵¹ Poche, “Einige Erwägungen über die Kameen Karls IV.,” 88–90; Kyzourová and Vlnas, *Žezlo a koruna*, 111–113.

⁵² Vítovský, “Zlatnictví na dvoře Václava II.,” 479; Žemlička, “Rituál přísahy,” 41–42.

⁵³ Witecki, “The Treasure Discovery Circumstances and Presentation,” 564–567.

who brought it to Prague from Paris?⁵⁴ Is it possible that it was used for her Bohemian coronation in 1347?

Another noteworthy crown is preserved in the treasury of the Munich Residenz. It became the property of the House of Wittelsbach in 1402 as the nuptial crown of English Princess Blanche (d. 1409). This crown originally belonged to the treasury of King Richard II of England and is believed to have arrived in England as the personal crown of Anne of Bohemia (d. 1394), daughter of Charles IV, who married Richard in 1382.⁵⁵ Although it was once thought to have been made in Prague, it is now considered more likely to have been crafted in Paris.⁵⁶

Regardless of the exact origins of these preserved crowns, it is evident that Prague in the latter half of the fourteenth century was not lacking in crowns, and each royal consort could afford her own diadem. Still, most accounts of the coronations of Bohemian queens in the Middle Ages are limited to brief references, offering little detailed information. As a result, these sources do not provide substantial evidence to support the thesis that a specific crown was designated exclusively for the coronation of queens, nor do they confirm the use of personal diadems for their coronations.

From the Luxembourg era, only one detailed description survives regarding the crown used during a queen's coronation. This account pertains to the 1400 coronation of Sophia of Bavaria, the second wife of Wenceslas IV.⁵⁷ According to the report, after the queen was crowned, two Bohemian lords held the crown above the queen's head ensuring it did not touch her, as "the gold crown, adorned with gems and pearls, was too heavy."⁵⁸ This description closely corresponds to the characteristics of the St. Wenceslas Crown. Furthermore, the unexplained absence of King Wenceslas IV from the ceremony strengthens the hypothesis that the St. Wenceslas Crown may have been used on this occasion without diminishing the splendour of royal majesty.

Nevertheless, two issues complicate this identification. First, the description of the crown could equally apply to most crowns housed in the treasury of St. Vitus Cathedral and therefore does not provide conclusive evidence that the St. Wenceslas Crown was used. Second, the account specifies that the crown was taken from the altar and the head of St. Vitus, where it had been ceremonially placed during a procession at the beginning of the mass. If this eyewitness report is credible, it is unlikely that the crown in question was the St. Wenceslas Crown, which would have more appropriately adorned the reliquary head of St. Wenceslas. This discrepancy suggests an intriguing hypothesis: while the crown designated for the reliquary of St. Wenceslas may have been used for the coronation of kings, the crown for the reliquary of St. Vitus might have been reserved for the coronation of queens.⁵⁹

However, medieval inventories of Prague Cathedral do not document the existence of any crown specifically intended for the reliquary of St. Vitus, in contrast to those associated with St. Wenceslas or St. Sigismund.⁶⁰ Still, the absence of such a crown in the inventories is not

⁵⁴ Cf. Kyzourová and Vlnas, *Žezlo a koruna*, 32–33.

⁵⁵ Twining, *A History of the Crown Jewels*, 27–28.

⁵⁶ Stratford, *Richard II and the English Royal Treasure*, 52, 258–262.

⁵⁷ For more details on this source, see Pacovský, *Svatojirský klášter*, 171–182.

⁵⁸ Pacovský, *Svatojirský klášter*, 186: [...] *per totum officium illius misse dominus Henricus de Rosemberg et dominus Brzenko de Skal tenuerunt coronam supra caput ipsius, non permittentes caput pertingere, quia corona aurea ornata lapidibus et margaritis gravis fuit [...].*

⁵⁹ It was suggested by Uličný, "Chóry," 53.

⁶⁰ Cf. Podlaha and Šittler, *Chrámový poklad*, III, XXX, XXXI.

necessarily decisive, as these adornments were typically recorded only if they had suffered damage or required repairs.⁶¹ The mentioned gilded silver head of St. Vitus was donated to the St. Vitus treasury by Charles IV in 1355 but was lost during the Hussite Wars (1419–1434). A new reliquary bust of St. Vitus was not created until the reign of King Vladislav II (r. 1471–1516), before 1500, but it no longer played a significant role in the coronations of queens. Similarly, the bust of St. Wenceslas, restored alongside that of St. Adalbert, was no longer designed for the placement of the royal crown.⁶²

Royal Crown on the Heads of Queens

The question arises, since when the Crown of St. Wenceslas had been used during the coronations of queen consorts of Bohemia. The crown was certainly used twenty years after the coronation of Queen Sophia, on 28 July 1420, for the coronation of her brother-in-law, King Sigismund (r. 1419–1437), who secretly took it out of the country shortly thereafter. It did not return to Bohemia until August 1436. After being transported via Jihlava to Prague, Emperor Sigismund presented himself with the “Bohemian crown” (*českú korunu*) as the rightful King of Bohemia at Old Town Square on 26 August 1436.⁶³ Because of the changed ecclesiastical and political situation, the crown was no longer entrusted to the care of the Prague Metropolitan Chapter.⁶⁴ At latest by the time of the coronation of Sigismund’s successor, King Albert of Habsburg, in 1438, it was placed under the protection of the Bohemian estates at Karlstein Castle in Central Bohemia.⁶⁵

Meanwhile, while the St. Wenceslas Crown was undoubtedly kept in Prague, another coronation took place at Prague Castle on 11 February 1437. In the presence of Emperor Sigismund (though it is not mentioned whether he wore any diadem), his wife, Barbara of Cilli, was crowned. Unlike the general reference in 1400 to a “golden crown” (*corona aurea*) being used, the chronicler Bartošek of Drahonice specifically noted that Barbara was crowned with the “Bohemian crown” (*Boemicali corona*).⁶⁶ All the circumstances therefore suggest that the St. Wenceslas Crown may indeed have been used. The necessity of using this crown, due to the absence of another precious diadem, would reflect the financial distress of Sigismund’s court and the kingdom, exhausted by prolonged wars. At the same time, a coronation with this revered crown could symbolise the restoration of royal authority without requiring Sigismund to be crowned again—an act he sought to avoid in order to uphold the legitimacy of his 1420 coronation.

The use of the St. Wenceslas Crown can be certainly assumed for the coronation of Johana of Rožmitál on 8 May 1458, the day after the coronation of her husband, George of Poděbrady. The memorial book of the deans of the Faculty of Arts of Prague University explicitly mentions that she bore the “royal crown” (*coronam regiam*) on her head, while no crown is noted as adorning the king’s head at the same time.⁶⁷ As it was already outlined, the lack on crowns was most probably the reason why the coronations of George and Johana were held separately.

⁶¹ Kodišová, “Zlatnické přírůstky,” 38.

⁶² Kuthan and Royt, *The Cathedral of St. Vitus at Prague Castle*, 276, 283, 331–333; Kyzourová and Vlnas, *Žezlo a koruna*, 86–88; cf. Podlaha and Šittler, *Chrámový poklad*, 46, XII.

⁶³ Palacký, *Dílo Františka Palackého* II, 94: [...] *Císařova Milost seděl v svém majestátu v Starém městě na rynku na stolicech povýšených pod českú korunu.*

⁶⁴ Skýbová, *České královské korunovační klenoty*, 38.

⁶⁵ Čornej, *Světla a stíny busitství*, 305–309.

⁶⁶ *Chronicon Bartossek de Drahonicz*, 619; cf. *Staré letopisy české*, 73; Dvořáková, *Barbara of Cilli*, 155.

⁶⁷ *Liber decanorum* II, s. 59: [...] *Girzi, qui corona capiti suo imposita deductus est solenniter cum candelis et vexillis in civitatem Pragensem usque domum suam. Item domina princeps regina, contoralis ejus, in crastino secunda feria per eosdem episcopos est inuncta et*

A single royal crown was also mentioned during King Louis' stay in Prague in 1522, when the coronation of his wife, Mary of Austria, was arranged.⁶⁸ This suggests that both spouses had to share the same crown on different occasions. Likewise, accounts of the 1527 coronations of Ferdinand I of Habsburg and his wife, Anna Jagiellon, indicate that the queen was crowned with the same crown as the king.⁶⁹ The coronation jewel of King Ferdinand, described as “a very beautiful old work with quite large gemstones”, was undoubtedly the preserved Crown of St. Wenceslas. This “royal crown” (*die königlich Krön*) was also placed upon the queen's head.⁷⁰

Since then, the use of the St. Wenceslas Crown in the coronations of Bohemian queens has been beyond doubt. Moreover, the arrangement of two separate coronation ceremonies, which deviated from the established tradition and the coronation *ordo* of Charles IV, would otherwise be inexplicable. Nevertheless, this was not the only change to the coronation rite of queen consorts following the Hussite Wars. Compared to earlier periods, the ceremony saw a more prominent role for the Supreme Burgrave of the Kingdom and especially to the Benedictine Abbess of St. George's Convent at Prague Castle.⁷¹ Another change likely concerned the coronation sermon—an integral part of the pre-Hussite coronation ceremony—which is not documented after the wars, with exceptions in 1527 and 1619,⁷² and may have been abandoned due to the tense religious climate.

Conclusion

Medieval sources on the crowns of Bohemian queens offer only limited information. It was customary for queen consorts not to be crowned with the same crown as the reigning kings, as demonstrated especially by the records of the coronations in 1297 and 1337. This practice remained unchanged even after the introduction of the new Crown of St. Wenceslas. Fourteenth-century accounts consistently associate the St. Wenceslas Crown solely with the coronation of kings. Queen consorts were likely crowned with other diadems kept at the royal court in Prague, as suggested not only by surviving diadems but also by references to crowns donated for the reliquary busts of saints housed in the treasury of Prague Cathedral.

A joint coronation of the royal couple during a single mass, as anticipated by Charles' coronation *ordo* for the Kingdom of Bohemia, generally required two crowns. The lack of crowns—or more precisely, the existence of only one coronation jewel—necessitated the division of the ceremony into two separate masses, as occurred in 1458. It is not possible to determine whether Johana of Rožmitál was the first queen to be crowned with the Crown of St. Wenceslas. She was probably not, as Barbara of Cilli was allegedly adorned with the “Bohemian crown” as early as 1437. Still, it seems much less likely that this crown was used in pre-Hussite times, when other diadems for queens were available in Prague. The question remains whether, during the reigns of Charles IV

coronata, et solenniter conducta eodem die in civitatem Pragensem comitatu magno dominorum, rege antecedente, et multitudine curruum; ubi insidens primo curru ferebat coronam regiam in capite suo, capillis pulcherrimis discriminatis, et vocata Johanna, quam Dominus Deus una cum rege suo dignetur sanam et incolumem conservare.

⁶⁸ *Paměti o bouři pražské roku 1524*, 306.

⁶⁹ Václav Hájek z Libočan, *Kronika česká*, 1091: *V neděli pak na den svatého Matěje apoštola Božího Král Jeho Milost, král Ferdinandus, v kostele svatého Víta na hradě Pražském s velikou slavností korunován a nazejtří Královna Anna Její Milost v témž kostele také touž korunou českou korunována.*

⁷⁰ *Sněmy české*, no. 159, 225–229.

⁷¹ Pacovský, “The Involvement of the Abbesses,” 97–99.

⁷² It is documented only during the coronation of Ferdinand I in 1527, but notably absent from the coronation of his wife, see *Sněmy české*, no. 159, 225–229; sermons were later delivered at the Protestant coronations of Frederick of the Palatinate and his wife, Elizabeth Stuart, in 1619, see Hrbek, *České barokní korunovace*, 91; Berning, “*Nach altem löblichen Gebrauch*”, 102–103, 142.

and Wenceslas IV, queens were consistently crowned with the same crown (possibly linked to the reliquary head of St. Vitus, as suggested by the account of the 1400 coronation), or whether they were crowned with their private crowns. Nevertheless, the practice of separating the coronation of the king and queen into two distinct days, introduced after the Hussite Wars, with the ancient St. Wenceslas Crown used at both ceremonies, became a longstanding tradition in early modern Bohemia.

The Bohemian coronations were profoundly shaped by Charles IV. In anticipation of his accession to the throne—and following the creation of an independent Czech ecclesiastical province—he composed a new coronation *ordo* and commissioned a new royal crown. Both were intended to reinforce the sacral and timeless nature of royal investiture, thereby stabilising and strengthening royal authority in Bohemia. Despite Charles’ significant role in formalising the Bohemian coronation ceremony, his influence was not definitive. Surprisingly, the Hussite Wars left a deep mark on these seemingly immutable rituals. Although the coronations remained deeply rooted in Roman Catholic liturgy—making no concessions to the Bohemian Reformation—and focused on reinforcing royal power, the weakening of both the royal court and the ecclesiastical hierarchy during the Hussite era led to notable shifts.

Unlike Charles IV’s deliberate interventions, these changes were unintended yet profound, particularly in elevating the role of women. Queen consorts gained direct access to the sacred crown of kings, while abbesses from nearby St. George’s Convent assumed roles traditionally reserved for bishops, including the handling of the royal crown itself. These anomalies—caused by a shortage of crowns and high-ranking clergy in the fifteenth-century “heretical” kingdom—ultimately became defining features of Bohemian queens’ coronations until the last coronation in 1836.⁷³

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Table: Coronations of Queen Consorts of Bohemia

Coronation Date	Queen Consort	Royal Husband	Crowned
1086, June 15	Svatava of Poland	Vratislav	alongside the king
1228, February 6	Cunigunde of Hohenstaufen	Wenceslas I	alongside the king
1261, December 25	Kunigunde of Hungary	Ottokar II	alongside the king
1297, June 2	Guta of Habsburg	Wenceslas II	alongside the king
1303, May 26	Elizabeth Richeza	Wenceslas II	separately after marrying crowned king
1311, February 7	Elizabeth of Bohemia	John	alongside the king
1337, May 18	Beatrice of Bourbon	John	separately after marrying crowned king
1347, September 2	Blanche of Valois	Charles IV	alongside the king
1349, November 1	Anna of Bavaria	Charles IV	separately after marrying crowned king
1353, July 28	Anna of Świdnica	Charles IV	separately after marrying crowned king
1363, June 18	Elizabeth of Pomerania	Charles IV	separately after marrying crowned king and after her stepson's coronation
1370, November 17	Joanna of Bavaria	Wenceslas IV	separately after marrying crowned king
1400, March 15	Sophia of Bavaria	Wenceslas IV	separately after marrying crowned king
1437, February 11	Barbara of Cilli	Sigismund	separately (husband crowned during the Hussite Wars)
1458, May 8	Joanna of Rožmitál	George of Poděbrady	separately after king's coronation
1522, June 1	Mary of Habsburg	Louis	separately after marrying crowned king
1527, February 25	Anna Jagiellon of Bohemia and Hungary	Ferdinand I	separately after king's coronation
1562, September 21	Maria of Spain	Maximilian II	separately after king's coronation
1616, January 10	Anna of Tyrol	Matthias II	separately after marrying crowned king
1619, November 7	Elizabeth Stuart	Frederick of the Palatinate	separately after king's coronation
1627, November 21	Eleonora Gonzaga	Ferdinand II	separately after marrying crowned king and before her stepson's coronation
1656, September 11	Eleonora Magdalena Gonzaga	Ferdinand III	separately after marrying crowned king and before her stepson's coronation
1723, September 8	Elizabeth Christine of Brunswick-Wolfenbüttel	Charles VI	separately after king's coronation
1791, September 12	Maria Luisa of Spain	Leopold II	separately after king's coronation
1792, August 11	Maria Theresa of Naples	Francis I	separately after king's coronation
1836, September 12	Maria Anna of Savoy	Ferdinand V	separately after king's coronation